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TRANSIENT MATHEMATICAL MODELS FOR TWO PHASE BINARY FLUIDS

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Summary

This work deals with the numerical modeling for two phase binary mixtures and one-dimensional flows. Three lumped capacitance models of increasing complexity suitable for two phase binary mixtures and one-dimensional flows are described. The base model considers homogeneous or separated flow in thermodynamic equilibrium, where separated flow is calculated through correlations for void fraction and vapor quality. Then, to consider countercurrent liquid and vapor flow, such as gravity driven liquid flow, a separated flow model in thermodynamic equilibrium is developed. The third and most complex model removes the thermodynamic equilibrium assumption and treats heat and mass transfer through the liquid vapor interface according to two-film theory. Ad hoc iterative procedures have been developed to calculate state variable derivatives, due to the implicit nature of the set of conservation equations, and time integration is performed by explicit, variable time step method. The resulting solvers are able to handle smoothly transition from compressible to quasi-incompressible flow, a situation that can be encountered within a component that is filled up with saturated or subcooled liquid.

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Introduction

In this work, dynamic mathematical models and iterative algorithms for two phase binary mixtures are developed with increasing complexity to model energy systems characterized by components with different functions and where different phenomena take place i.e., condensation, evaporation, absorption. The following three models have been developed.

1. Dynamic model for homogeneous and separated flow in thermodynamic equilibrium (Section 1)

This model is similar to what was described in (Goyal and Garimella, 2019), assuming homogeneous flow in thermodynamic equilibrium. Then, separated liquid and vapor flows are considered through existing correlations for vapor quality and void fraction.

2. Dynamic model for separated flow in thermodynamic equilibrium (Section 2)

This model takes into account countercurrent flows between liquid and vapor and gravity driven liquid flows. Countercurrent flows of liquid and vapor cannot be considered by existing correlations described in the previous model.

3. Dynamic model for separated flow and thermodynamic equilibrium at the interface (Section 3)

This model also considers the interaction between liquid and vapor, calculating the interface temperature and heat and mass transfers through the interface

Then, a brief description of the incompressible flow model is provided in Section 4.

1. Dynamic model for homogeneous and separated flow in thermodynamic equilibrium

The model described in this section for binary fluids is based on the following main assumptions:

- 1D compressible Newtonian fluid (MacArthur and Grald, 1989)
- Thermodynamic equilibrium between liquid and vapor (Qiao et al., 2015)
- Uniform and time variant pressure. Pressure wave propagates significantly faster than thermal and mass storage effects (MacArthur and Grald, 1989)
- Pressure drops are neglected, leading to the omission of the momentum conservation equation (Goyal and Garimella, 2019)
- Negligible axial conduction effects. The Peclet number is typically large (Qiao et al., 2015)
- Negligible viscous dissipation and body forces (Qiao et al., 2015)
- Inlet and Outlet mass flow rates, mass fractions and enthalpies are known, i.e., defined by other components as expansion valves

Figure 1: Scheme of the homogeneous flow model in thermodynamic equilibrium

Mass, species and energy conservation equations (Equation (1), Equation (2), and Equation (3)) are imposed to each control volume to calculate the variations of mass fraction ($d X_i / dt$), enthalpy ($d h_i / dt$) and pressure (dP / dt) and the mass flow rate (\dot{m}_{j+1} , see Figure 1). The implicit nature of the set of equations and the two available directions of mass flow rates, i.e. mass flows from node i to node $i+1$ or in the opposite direction, lead to develop the iterative procedure described in Section 1.1. The homogenous flow assumption is often considered when liquid and vapor are in thermodynamic equilibrium, assuming that they have the same velocity. However, this may not be accurate for some components i.e., evaporator with an annular flow (Qiao et al., 2015), thus X_j and h_j are calculated considering existing correlations for vapor quality and void fraction as described in Section 1.1. Once the state variables derivatives are calculated, pressure, mass fraction, and enthalpy of each control volume are updated considering an explicit integration and a variable time step calculated as in Section 1.2.

$$\frac{d(\rho_i V_i)}{dt} = \dot{m}_j - \dot{m}_{j+1} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{d(\rho_i V_i X_i)}{dt} = \dot{m}_j X_j - \dot{m}_{j+1} X_{j+1} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{d(\rho_i V_i (h_i - v_i P))}{dt} = \dot{m}_j h_j - \dot{m}_{j+1} h_{j+1} + \sum \dot{Q}_i \quad (3)$$

1.1 Solver

The following iterative procedure is developed to calculate the state variable derivatives from the conservation equations imposed to each control volume.

1. Guess $\frac{dP}{dt}$
2. Guess the direction of \dot{m}_j that can be either from $i-1$ to i or in the opposite direction. In the former case, X_j and h_j are calculated in Equation (4) and Equation (5), otherwise X_{L_i} , X_{V_i} , h_{L_i} , and h_{V_i} are considered instead of $X_{L_{i-1}}$, $X_{V_{i-1}}$, $h_{L_{i-1}}$, and $h_{V_{i-1}}$. The slip ratio based on void fraction correlations is calculated in Equation (6) (Qiao et al., 2015). The thermodynamic properties are related to the control volume of the leaving mass flow rate, while the coefficients C_1 , C_2 , C_3 , and C_4 can be found in Table 1 for different void fraction correlation (Qiao et al., 2015).

$$X_j = X_{L_{i-1}}(1 - \hat{a}_j) + X_{V_{i-1}} \hat{a}_j \quad (4)$$

$$h_j = h_{L_{i-1}}(1 - \hat{a}_j) + h_{V_{i-1}} \hat{a}_j \quad (5)$$

$$\hat{a}_j = \frac{a_{i-1}^{1/C_2}}{a_{i-1}^{1/C_2} + \left[\frac{1}{C_1} \left(\frac{\rho_{L_{i-1}}}{\rho_{V_{i-1}}} \right)^{C_3} \left(\frac{\mu_{V_{i-1}}}{\mu_{L_{i-1}}} \right)^{C_4} \right]^{1/C_2}} (1 - a_{i-1})^{1/C_2} \quad (6)$$

Table 1: Constant and exponents for various void fraction models (source:(Qiao et al., 2015))

Models	C1	C2	C3	C4
Homogeneous	1	1	1	0
(Zivi, 1964)	1	1	0.67	0
(Turner, 1966)	1	0.72	0.4	0.08
(Smith, 1969)	0.79	0.78	0.58	0
(Lockhart and Martinelli, 1949)	0.28	0.64	0.36	0.07
(Thom, 1964)	1	1	0.89	0.18
(Baroczy, 1963)	1	0.74	0.65	0.13

3. Calculate \dot{m}_{j+1} , mass fraction and enthalpy variations by solving the set of conservation equations. Equation (7), Equation (8), and Equation (9) are obtained developing Equation (1),

Equation (2), and Equation (3) as described in Appendix A. The coefficients a_{MPi} , a_{MXi} , and a_{Mhi} are calculated in Equation (10), Equation (11), and Equation (12)

$$a_{MPi} \frac{dP}{dt} + a_{MXi} \frac{dX_i}{dt} + a_{Mhi} \frac{dh_i}{dt} = \dot{m}_j - \dot{m}_{j+1} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{dX_i}{dt} = \frac{\dot{m}_j(X_j - X_i) - \dot{m}_{j+1}(X_{j+1} - X_i)}{\rho_i V_i} \quad (8)$$

$$\left(V_i h_i \frac{\partial \rho_i}{\partial P} - V_i \right) \frac{dP}{dt} + \left(V_i h_i \frac{\partial \rho_i}{\partial X} \right) \frac{dX_i}{dt} + \left(V_i h_i \frac{\partial \rho_i}{\partial h} + \rho_i V_i \right) \frac{dh_i}{dt} = \dot{m}_j h_j - \dot{m}_{j+1} h_{j+1} + \sum \dot{Q}_i \quad (9)$$

$$a_{MPi} = V_i \frac{\partial \rho_i}{\partial P} \quad (10)$$

$$a_{MXi} = V_i \frac{\partial \rho_i}{\partial X} \quad (11)$$

$$a_{Mhi} = V_i \frac{\partial \rho_i}{\partial h} \quad (12)$$

4. Verify that all the calculated \dot{m}_j have the same direction of the guess. If the directions are not coherent return to point 2 using the calculated directions as new guess.
5. The error is calculated on the overall mass balance (Equation (13)), obtained by adding the mass balances (Equation (7)) for each control volume.

$$err = \sum_{i=1}^N a_{MPi} \frac{dP}{dt} + \sum_{i=1}^N a_{MXi} \frac{dX_i}{dt} + \sum_{i=1}^N a_{Mhi} \frac{dh_i}{dt} - \dot{m}_{in} + \dot{m}_{out} \quad (13)$$

6. Verify that the error calculated at point 5 is lower than the maximum accepted error, otherwise return to point 1. The new guess of the pressure variation could be calculated with different methods such as the under-relaxation method, the secant method, the Newton-Raphson method, or a combination of them.

The solver described above is valid for two-phase conditions, but it may not converge for quasi-incompressible conditions due to the increased stiffness of the numerical problem. The quasi-incompressible condition means that the density is mainly function of mass fraction and temperature i.e., every volume of a component is filled with saturated or subcooled liquid. For quasi-incompressible conditions, the pressure variation, inlet flow rate and related thermodynamic properties are provided as inputs, i.e., the pressure variation of the component under analysis is assumed equal to the one of a component directly connected. Thus, the same set of equations is considered (Equations (7), (8), and (9)). The overall mass balance for quasi-incompressible conditions is thus automatically verified considering the outlet mass flow rate equal to \dot{m}_{N+1} calculated by the set of conservation equations,

simplifying the calculation process avoiding the iterative procedure. The quasi-incompressible condition is also solved providing as input the outlet mass flow rate instead of the inlet one. Moreover, inlet and outlet mass flow rate are usually allocated to the first volume and the last volume of the component, but the described solver accepts multiple inputs and outputs in different positions of the component, i.e., an additional input/output in an intermediate volume.

1.2 Variable time step

The explicit integration scheme, selected for its simplicity in the implementation, coupled with a variable time step needs an accurate calculation of the time step to avoid numerical instability. The time step is calculated considering the following conditions:

- $\left| \frac{dP}{dt} \right| \Delta t < \Delta P_{max}$
- $\left| \frac{dX_i}{dt} \right| \Delta t < \Delta X_{max}$
- $\left| \frac{dh_i}{dt} \right| \Delta t < \Delta h_{max}$
- $\frac{M_i}{|\dot{m}_j|} * 0.5 > \Delta t \quad \text{if } (\dot{m}_j \neq 0)$
- $\frac{M_{i-1}}{|\dot{m}_j|} * 0.5 > \Delta t \quad \text{if } (\dot{m}_j \neq 0)$
- $\Delta t \leq \Delta t_{max}$

The time step is calculated for every control volume and the minimum value is selected to perform the integration. The thresholds in Table 2 can be used to achieve a balance between computational speed and accuracy of results.

Table 2: Thresholds for variable time step calculation

Threshold	Value	Unit of measurement
ΔP_{max}	100	<i>Pa</i>
ΔX_{max}	0.05	<i>kg kg⁻¹</i>
Δh_{max}	1000	<i>J kg⁻¹</i>
Δt_{max}	0.1	<i>s</i>

2. Dynamic model for separated flow in thermodynamic equilibrium

The model described in this section for binary fluids considers separated flows and thermodynamic equilibrium between liquid and vapor in every control volume. The improvement introduced in this model compared to the one described in Section 1 is that liquid and vapor mass flow rates between two control volumes can have opposite directions (compare Figure 1 and Figure 2), this could be essential for specific components, i.e., distillation columns. The assumptions described in Section 1 are still valid.

Figure 3: Scheme of separated flows between two control volumes in thermodynamic equilibrium

Figure 2: Scheme of the separated flow model in thermodynamic equilibrium

Mass, species and energy conservation equations (Equation (14), Equation (15), and Equation (16)) are imposed to each control volume (see Figure 2) to calculate mass fraction variation (dX_i/dt), enthalpy variation (dh_i/dt), pressure variation (dP/dt) and vapor mass flow rate (\dot{m}_{Vj+1}). The iterative procedure in Section 2.2 is needed due to the implicit nature of the set of equations and the two possible directions for the mass flow rate (\dot{m}_{Vj}). The liquid mass flow rate (\dot{m}_{Lj}) is calculated as in Section 2.1 as a function of the internal geometry of the component, its position, and the thermophysical properties of the fluid, i.e., gravity driven liquid flow in a vertical component (see Figure 2). \dot{m}_{Vj} is related to vapor when a significant amount of vapor is present in the outlet control volume. However, for void fractions close to zero, \dot{m}_{Vj} is divided into the effective vapor mass flow rate $k_j \dot{m}_{Vj}$ and the additional liquid mass flow rate $(1-k_j) \dot{m}_{Vj}$ for which the thermodynamic properties of

the liquid are considered (see Figure 3). k_j is the vapor fraction of \dot{m}_{V_j} and it is calculated as function of the void fraction of the outlet control volume i.e., \dot{m}_{V_j} depends on a_{i-1} when \dot{m}_{V_j} flows from control volume $i-1$ to i . k_j should be set equal to zero when the void fraction of the outlet control volume is zero, while it should be set equal to one when \dot{m}_{V_j} is vapor. In between, k_j is calculated by a function that in this work has been assumed to be a linear function. X_{L_j} , h_{L_j} , X_{V_j} , and h_{V_j} are set equal to $X_{L_{i-1}}$, $h_{L_{i-1}}$, $X_{V_{i-1}}$, and $h_{V_{i-1}}$ or X_{L_j} , h_{L_j} , X_{V_j} , and h_{V_j} based on liquid (\dot{m}_{L_j}) and vapor ($k_j \dot{m}_{V_j}$) flow directions respectively, while $X_{L_j}^*$ and $h_{L_j}^*$ are set equal to X_{L_i} and h_{L_i} when $(1-k_j)\dot{m}_{V_j}$ flows from i to $i-1$, otherwise they are set equal to $X_{L_{i-1}}$ and $h_{L_{i-1}}$. Once the state variable derivatives are calculated, pressure, mass fraction, and enthalpy of each control volume are updated considering an explicit integration and a variable time step calculated as in Section 2.3.

$$\frac{d\rho_i V_i}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} + k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} + (1-k_j) \dot{m}_{V_j} - (1-k_{j+1}) \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{d\rho_i V_i X_i}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} X_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} X_{L_j} + k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} X_{V_j} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} X_{V_{j+1}} + (1-k_j) \dot{m}_{V_j} X_{L_j}^* - (1-k_{j+1}) \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} X_{L_{j+1}}^* \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{d\rho_i V_i (h_i - v_i P)}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} h_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} h_{L_j} + k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} h_{V_j} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} h_{V_{j+1}} + (1-k_j) \dot{m}_{V_j} h_{L_j}^* - (1-k_{j+1}) \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} h_{L_{j+1}}^* \quad (16)$$

2.1 Liquid mass flow rate

The liquid mass flow rate depends on the internal geometry of the component, the mass of liquid in the considered control volume, and the liquid thermophysical properties. The following approaches are considered for different geometries:

- The liquid mass flow rate for a porous matrix, as the case of packed columns, is calculated as function of the liquid hold up, defined as the ratio between liquid volume ($V_{L,i}$) and overall volume (V_i). The total hold up is the sum of the static hold up ($H_{s,i}$) and the dynamic hold up ($H_{d,i}$). The first considers the liquid that remains suspended in the column when liquid and vapor flows are interrupted, while the second takes into account the liquid volume that drains from the column (Zarzycki and Chacuk, 1993). Equation (17) and Equation (18) are correlations for static and dynamic hold up that were obtained correlating experimental results performed for different geometries of packed columns (Takahashi et al., 1979; Zarzycki and Chacuk, 1993). The static hold up was mainly dependent on the packing size ($L_{c,i}$), while the dynamic hold up is also function of the void fraction of the packed bed (E_i), the liquid Reynolds number ($Re_{L,i}$) (see Equation (19)), and the viscosity of liquid ($\mu_{L,i}$) and water ($\mu_{H_2O,i}$) at the same temperature and pressure (Takahashi et al., 1979). Combining Equation (18) and Equation (19), the liquid mass flow rate is calculated in Equation (20). For applications where chemical reactions are not present, the influence of static hold up is negligible, while for

applications with chemical reactions, the static hold up should be considered (Zarzycki and Chacuk, 1993).

$$H_{s,i} = 1.53 * 10^{-4} L_{c,i}^{-1.2} \quad (17)$$

$$H_{d,i} = 2.9 * 10^{-5} E_i R e_{L,i}^{0.66} \left(\frac{\mu_{L,i}}{\mu_{H_2O,i}} \right)^{0.75} L_{c,i}^{-1.2} \quad (18)$$

$$R e_{L,i} = \frac{w_{L,i} L_{c,i}}{\mu_{L,i} E_i} = \frac{\dot{m}_{L,i} L_{c,i}}{A_{c,i} \mu_{L,i} E_i} \quad (19)$$

$$\dot{m}_{L_j} = \left(H_{d,i} \left(2.9 * 10^{-5} E_i \left(\frac{L_{c,i}}{A_{c,i} \mu_{L,i} E_i} \right)^{0.66} \left(\frac{\mu_{L,i}}{\mu_{H_2O,i}} \right)^{0.75} L_{c,i}^{-1.2} \right)^{-1} \right)^{1/0.66} \quad (20)$$

- For the case of plate sections, the gravity driven liquid flow is calculated assuming that liquid flows through holes in a plate, thus the ideal velocity is calculated with Torricelli's law (see Equation (21)), where the height of the liquid on the plate is equal to the ratio between the volume of liquid ($V_i (1-a_i)$) and area of the plate ($A_{c,plate,i}$). The real velocity is calculated multiplying the ideal velocity by the discharge coefficient (Franchini and Lanza, 2014) that could be roughly assumed equal to 0.6 (Teoman et al., 2022). The total liquid mass flow rate is calculated in Equation (21), where $A_{c,holes,i}$ is the difference between the overall cross section area and the area of the plate.

$$\dot{m}_{L_j} = \rho_{L,i} A_{c,holes,i} 0.6 \left(2 g \frac{V_i (1-a_i)}{A_{c,plate,i}} \right)^{0.5} \quad (21)$$

The liquid mass flow rates calculated in Equation (20) and Equation (21) assume that in the control volume below is present a vapor or a two-phase condition. The following strategy has been developed to deal with the condition where the lower control volume could be filled with saturated or sub-cooled liquid:

- If $0 \leq a_{i-1} < a_{threshold\ 1}$: \dot{m}_{L_j} is the minimum between $\dot{m}_{L_{j-1}}$ and $\dot{m}_{L_j}^*$, that is the value calculated in Equation (20) or Equation (21), depending on the considered geometry.
- If $a_{threshold\ 1} \leq a_{i-1} \leq a_{threshold\ 2}$: \dot{m}_{L_j} is calculated in Equation (22). The factor f_j varies between 0 and 1 for $a_{i-1} = a_{threshold\ 1}$ and $a_{i-1} = a_{threshold\ 2}$, i.e., linear function, polynomial function.

$$\dot{m}_{L_j} = \min(\dot{m}_{L_{j-1}}, \dot{m}_{L_j}^*) (1-f_j) + \dot{m}_{L_j}^* f_j \quad (22)$$

- If $a_{i-1} > a_{threshold\ 2}$: \dot{m}_{L_j} is equal to $\dot{m}_{L_j}^*$.

Where $a_{threshold\ 1}$ and $a_{threshold\ 2}$ are two parameters that need to be set. For this work, $a_{threshold\ 1} = 0.01$ and $a_{threshold\ 2} = 0.1$ have been used.

2.2 Solver

The following iterative procedure is developed to calculate the state derivatives from conservation equations imposed to each control volume.

1. Guess $\frac{dP}{dt}$
2. Guess the direction of \dot{m}_{Vj} . It could flow from $i-1$ to i or in the opposite way. X_{Vj} , h_{Vj} , X_{Lj} , h_{Lj} , X_{Lj}^* and h_{Lj}^* are set based on liquid and vapor directions as in Section 2.
3. Solve the set of conservation equations to calculate mass fraction variation, enthalpy variation, and \dot{m}_{Vj+1} . Equations (23), (24), and (25) are obtained developing Equations (14), (15), and (16) as described in Appendix B. The coefficients a_{MPi} , a_{MXi} , and a_{Mhi} are calculated in Equations (10), (11), and (12)

$$a_{MPi} \frac{dP}{dt} + a_{MXi} \frac{dX_i}{dt} + a_{Mhi} \frac{dh_i}{dt} = \dot{m}_{Lj+1} - \dot{m}_{Lj} + k_j \dot{m}_{Vj} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{Vj+1} + (1 - k_j) \dot{m}_{Vj} - (1 - k_{j+1}) \dot{m}_{Vj+1} \quad (23)$$

$$\rho_i V_i \frac{dX_i}{dt} = \dot{m}_{Lj+1} (X_{Lj+1} - X_{Li}) - \dot{m}_{Lj} (X_{Lj} - X_{Li}) + k_j \dot{m}_{Vj} (X_{Vj} - X_{Vi}) - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{Vj+1} (X_{Vj+1} - X_{Vi}) + (1 - \quad (24)$$

$$\left(V_i h_i \frac{\partial \rho_i}{\partial P} - V_i \right) \frac{dP}{dt} + \left(V_i h_i \frac{\partial \rho_i}{\partial X} \right) \frac{dX_i}{dt} + \left(V_i h_i \frac{\partial \rho_i}{\partial h} + \rho_i V_i \right) \frac{dh_i}{dt} = \dot{m}_{Lj+1} h_{Lj+1} - \dot{m}_{Lj} h_{Lj} + k_j \dot{m}_{Vj} h_{Vj} - \quad (25)$$

4. Verify that all the calculated \dot{m}_{Vj} have the same direction of the guess. If the directions are not coherent return to point 2 using the calculated directions as new guess.
5. The error is calculated on the overall mass balance (see Equation (26)), obtained from the sum of the mass balances of each control volume.

$$err = \sum_{i=1}^N a_{MPi} \frac{dP}{dt} + \sum_{i=1}^N a_{MXi} \frac{dX_i}{dt} + \sum_{i=1}^N a_{Mhi} \frac{dh_i}{dt} - \dot{m}_{V_{in}} + \dot{m}_{V_{out}} - \dot{m}_{L_{in}} + \dot{m}_{L_{out}} \quad (26)$$

6. Verify that the error calculated at point 5 is lower than the maximum accepted error, otherwise return to point 1. The new guess of the pressure variation could be calculated with different methods such as the under-relaxation method, the secant method, the Newton-Raphson method, or a combination of them.

2.3 Variable time step

The explicit integration scheme coupled with a variable time step needs an accurate calculation of the time step. The variable time step is calculated based on conditions described in Section 1.2, with the difference that for this model the following specific conditions on M_L and M_V are needed to guarantee that enough liquid and vapor are present compared to liquid and vapor mass flows.

$$- \frac{M_{Li}}{|\dot{m}_{Lj}|} * 0.5 > \Delta t \quad \text{if } (\dot{m}_{Lj} \neq 0)$$

$$- \frac{M_{L_{i-1}}}{|\dot{m}_{L_j}|} * 0.5 > \Delta t \quad \text{if } (\dot{m}_{L_j} \neq 0)$$

$$- \frac{M_{V_i}}{|\dot{m}_{V_j}|} * 0.5 > \Delta t \quad \text{if } (\dot{m}_{V_j} \neq 0)$$

$$- \frac{M_{V_{i-1}}}{|\dot{m}_{V_j}|} * 0.5 > \Delta t \quad \text{if } (\dot{m}_{V_j} \neq 0)$$

3. Dynamic model for separated flow and thermodynamic equilibrium at the interface

The model for binary fluids described in this section is based on thermodynamic equilibrium at the interface and separated flows. With this approach, temperature and mass fraction of bulk liquid and bulk vapor may deviate from their respective phase equilibrium values. The model is based on the following main assumptions:

- One dimensional compressible flow of a two-phase binary mixture (Goyal and Garimella, 2019)
- Uniform and time variant pressure in the component (Roeder et al., 2019)
- Pressure drops are neglected. The momentum conservation equation is not considered (Goyal and Garimella, 2019)
- Separated two phase flows
- Homogeneous properties in liquid and vapor sub volumes
- Negligible viscous dissipations (Roeder et al., 2019)
- Negligible axial conduction effect as the Peclet number is typically large (Roeder et al., 2019)
- Inlet/Outlet liquid and vapor mass flow rates, mass fractions, and enthalpies are known, i.e., defined by other components as expansion valves

Figure 4: Scheme of separated flow model in thermodynamic equilibrium at the interface

Figure 5: Scheme of flow interactions between two control volumes that use separated flow model in thermodynamic equilibrium and in thermodynamic equilibrium at the interface

Mass, species, and energy conservation equations are imposed to liquid and vapor sub volumes (see Figure 4) to calculate the variations of liquid mass fraction, liquid enthalpy, vapor mass fraction, vapor enthalpy, pressure and void fraction, plus the vapor mass flow rate ($\dot{m}_{V_{j+1}}$). The implicit nature of the set of conservation equations, composed by Equations from (27) to (32), requires the use of the

iterative procedure described in Section 3.2. Temperature and mass fraction deviations from the equilibrium phase for liquid and vapor sub volumes lead to heat ($\dot{Q}_{L \int, i}$, $\dot{Q}_{V \int, i}$) and mass ($\dot{m}_{A_{Li}}$, $\dot{m}_{B_{Li}}$, $\dot{m}_{A_{Vi}}$, $\dot{m}_{B_{Vi}}$) transfers through the interface (see Figure 6), where A and B are two different species. The two-phase model described in Section 3.1 is implemented to calculate interface temperature and heat and mass transfers through the interface (Fernández-Seara et al., 2002). In addition to the transfers through the interface, an evaporation process could take place in the liquid sub volume, i.e., by external heat input, thus the produced vapor is transferred to the vapor sub volume considering the mass flow rate ($\dot{m}_{eva p_i}$), mass fraction ($X_{eva p_i}$) and enthalpy ($h_{eva p_i}$) of the evaporated fraction. Similarly, a condensation of the vapor could take place. In this case, the mass flow rate (\dot{m}_{cond_i}), the mass fraction (X_{cond_i}), and the enthalpy (h_{cond_i}) of the condensate are introduced. \dot{m}_{evap_i} and \dot{m}_{cond_i} are proportional to vapor and liquid masses in liquid and vapor sub volumes respectively. X_{evap_i} , h_{evap_i} , X_{cond_i} , and h_{cond_i} are calculated considering the thermodynamic equilibrium with liquid and vapor bulks respectively. \dot{m}_{V_j} could flow in both the directions as described in Section 3.2, while \dot{m}_{L_j} is calculated as described in Section 2.1. However, the separated model with liquid and vapor sub volumes is accurate when there are significant quantities of liquid and vapor in the control volume. Thus, when the a_i is close to zero or close to one, the assumption of thermodynamic equilibrium between the two phases is added obtaining the model in Section 2. The two models are supposed to be used simultaneously for different control volumes of the same component, with differential controller based on pre-defined thresholds ($a_{threshold 3}$, $a_{threshold 4}$, $a_{threshold 5}$, $a_{threshold 6}$) switches between them. k_j is set equal to one for the outlet fluid from the control volume that considers the model for separated flows and thermodynamic equilibrium at the interface, while the additional inlet liquid ($(1-k_j)\dot{m}_{V_j}$) should be properly allocated in the liquid sub volume as shown in Figure 5. Once the state variable derivatives are calculated, pressure, void fraction, liquid mass fraction, liquid enthalpy, vapor mass fraction, and vapor enthalpy of every control volume are integrated considering a variable time step as described in Section 3.3.

$$\frac{dM_{L_i}}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} + \dot{m}_{A_j} + \dot{m}_{B_j} + \dot{m}_{cond_i} - \dot{m}_{evap_i} + (1-k_j)\dot{m}_{V_j} - (1-k_{j+1})\dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} \quad (27)$$

$$\frac{dM_{L_i} X_{L_i}}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} X_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} X_{L_j} + \dot{m}_{A_j} + \dot{m}_{cond_i} X_{cond_i} - \dot{m}_{evap_i} X_{eva p_i} + (1-k_j)\dot{m}_{V_j} X_{L_{i-1}} - (1-k_{j+1})\dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} X_{L_i} \quad (28)$$

$$\frac{dM_{L_i} (h_{L_i} - v_{L_i} P)}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} h_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} h_{L_j} + \dot{m}_{A_{Vi}} \tilde{h}_{A_{Vi}} + \dot{m}_{B_{Vi}} \tilde{h}_{B_{Vi}} + \dot{m}_{cond_i} h_{cond_i} - \dot{m}_{evap_i} h_{eva p_i} + (1-k_j)\dot{m}_{V_j} h_{L_{i-1}} \quad (29)$$

$$\frac{dM_{V_i}}{dt} = k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{A_{Vi}} - \dot{m}_{B_{Vi}} - \dot{m}_{cond_i} + \dot{m}_{evap_i} \quad (30)$$

$$\frac{dM_{V_i} X_{V_i}}{dt} = k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} X_{V_j} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} X_{V_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{A_{Vi}} - \dot{m}_{cond_i} X_{cond_i} + \dot{m}_{evap_i} X_{eva p_i} \quad (31)$$

$$\frac{dM_{V_i}(h_{V_i} - v_{V_i}P)}{dt} = k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} h_{V_j} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} h_{V_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{A_{vi}} \tilde{h}_{A_{vi}} - \dot{m}_{B_{vi}} \tilde{h}_{B_{vi}} - \dot{m}_{cond_i} h_{cond_i} + \dot{m}_{evap_i} h_{evap_i} + \sum \dot{Q}_{V_i} \quad (32)$$

3.1 Interface model

The interface model to calculate temperature of the interface, heat and mass transfers through the interface is based on the following main assumptions:

- One-dimensional steady state model.
- No chemical reactions are taking place (Aminyavari et al., 2017).
- The interface mass fractions of vapor and liquid are in equilibrium at $T_{f,i}$ (Lewis and Whitman, 1924).
- Heat and mass transfer surfaces are equal, and heat and mass transfer resistances are confined to a thin region close to the interface (Bird et al., 2002).
- Kinetic, potential, and mechanical energy variations are neglected (Sieres and Fernández-Seara, 2007).
- No significant mass is stored in the interface (Fernández-Seara et al., 2002).

The mass transfer between vapor and liquid phases is the combination of molecular diffusion and bulk transport of material through the interface (Fernández-Seara et al., 2002). The absence of chemical reactions coupled with no stored mass in the interface leads to continuity of the molar flux for every species (A and B) as shown in Equation (33) and Equation (34) (see Figure 6).

$$\ddot{n}_{A L,i} = -\ddot{n}_{A V,i} = \ddot{n}_{A,i} \quad (33)$$

$$\ddot{n}_{B L,i} = -\ddot{n}_{B V,i} = \ddot{n}_{B,i} \quad (34)$$

Figure 6: Scheme of the interface model

The molar flux $\ddot{n}_{A L,i}$ that flows from the interface to the liquid is calculated as in Equation (35) (Bird et al., 2002). $\ddot{n}_{tot,i}$ is the sum of $\ddot{n}_{A,i}$ and $\ddot{n}_{B,i}$, $x_{A L \infty,i}$ is the liquid bulk molar fraction and $x_{A L 0,i}$ is the interface molar fraction. On the vapor side, $\ddot{n}_{A V,i}$ is calculated in Equation (36). $\ddot{n}_{tot,i}$ is considered positive when flows from the interface to liquid bulk, thus the minus in Equation (36). $x_{A V \infty,i}$ is the vapor bulk molar fraction and $x_{A V 0,i}$ is the interface molar fraction. The high net mass transfer rates across the interface provide a distortion of the boundary layer profiles of velocity, mass fraction, temperature, and thicknesses (Bird et al., 2002), influencing the friction factors and transfer

coefficients. Correction factors for the mass transfer coefficients ($\psi_{mL,i}$ and $\psi_{mV,i}$) are calculated in Equation (37) and Equation (38) (Bird et al., 2002) as function of $\phi_{mL,i}$ and $\phi_{mV,i}$ defined as the ratios between $\ddot{n}_{tot,i}$ and the respective mass transfer coefficient (F_{Li} or F_{Vi}). The mass transfer coefficients are calculated as described in (Onda et al., 1968) for a packed column and as in (Onda et al., 1968) and (Delahanty et al., 2021) for other geometries.

$$\ddot{n}_{A L,i} = \psi_{mL,i} F_{Li} (x_{A L0,i} - x_{A L\infty,i}) + x_{A L0,i} \ddot{n}_{tot,i} \quad (35)$$

$$\ddot{n}_{A V,i} = \psi_{mV,i} F_{Vi} (x_{A V0,i} - x_{A V\infty,i}) - x_{A V0,i} \ddot{n}_{tot,i} \quad (36)$$

$$\psi_{mL,i} = \frac{\phi_{mL,i}}{e^{\phi_{mL,i}} - 1} \quad (37)$$

$$\psi_{mV,i} = \frac{\phi_{mV,i}}{e^{\phi_{mV,i}} - 1} \quad (38)$$

The heat exchanged between interface and liquid and between interface and vapor is calculated as in Equations (39) and (40) respectively. The correction factors for the heat transfer coefficients related to interface distortion are calculated as in Equations (41) and (42). Heat transfer coefficients are calculated considering the Chilton-Colburn analogy (Chilton and Colburn, 1934), while the expressions for $\phi_{hL,i}$ and $\phi_{hV,i}$ can be found in Equation (43) and Equation (44) (Bird et al., 2002).

$$\dot{Q}_{L f,i} = \alpha_{Li} A_i \psi_{hL,i} (T_{f,i} - T_{L,i}) + \ddot{n}_{A L,i} \bar{h}_{L A,i} + \ddot{n}_{B L,i} \bar{h}_{L B,i} \quad (39)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{V f,i} = \alpha_{Vi} A_i \psi_{hV,i} (T_{f,i} - T_{V,i}) + \ddot{n}_{A V,i} \bar{h}_{V A,i} + \ddot{n}_{B V,i} \bar{h}_{V B,i} \quad (40)$$

$$\psi_{hL,i} = \frac{\phi_{hL,i}}{e^{\phi_{hL,i}} - 1} \quad (41)$$

$$\psi_{hV,i} = \frac{\phi_{hV,i}}{e^{\phi_{hV,i}} - 1} \quad (42)$$

$$\phi_{hL,i} = \frac{\ddot{n}_{A L,i} \bar{C}_{p AL,i} + \ddot{n}_{B L,i} \bar{C}_{p BL,i}}{\alpha_{Li}} \quad (43)$$

$$\phi_{hV,i} = \frac{\ddot{n}_{A V,i} \bar{C}_{p AV,i} + \ddot{n}_{B V,i} \bar{C}_{p BV,i}}{\alpha_{Vi}} \quad (44)$$

T_{int_i} and $\ddot{n}_{tot,i}$ are unknown from the beginning. Thus, the following nested iterative procedure is needed:

1. Guess T_{int_i} .
2. Update quantities related to T_{int_i} ($X_{A L0,i}$, $h_{A L,i}$, etc.).
3. Guess $\ddot{n}_{tot,i}$.
4. Calculate $\ddot{n}_{A L,i}$ and $\ddot{n}_{A V,i}$ with Equations (35) and (36) respectively.
5. Verify that $|\ddot{n}_{A L,i} - \ddot{n}_{A V,i}| < er r_{max,n}$ otherwise go back to point 3.
6. Calculate $\dot{Q}_{L f,i}$ and $\dot{Q}_{V f,i}$ with Equations (39) and (40) respectively.
7. Verify that $|\dot{Q}_{L f,i} - \dot{Q}_{V f,i}| < er r_{max,Q}$, otherwise go back to point 1.

Then, \dot{m}_{A_i} and \dot{m}_{B_i} are calculated multiplying $\ddot{n}_{A,i}$ and $\ddot{n}_{B,i}$ by the molar mass of A or B, and the interface area that is calculated as in (Onda et al., 1968) for the packed columns and as in (Akita and Yoshida, 1974) for other geometries.

3.2 Solver

The following iterative procedure is developed to calculate the state derivatives from conservation equations imposed to each control volume.

1. Guess dP/dt .
2. Guess the direction of \dot{m}_{V_j} . It could flow from $i-1$ to i or in the opposite way. X_{V_j} , h_{V_j} , X_{L_j} and h_{L_j} are set based on the direction of \dot{m}_{V_j} and \dot{m}_{L_j} respectively.
3. Solve the set of conservation equations to calculate the variations of liquid mass fraction, liquid enthalpy, vapor mass fraction, vapor enthalpy and void fraction, plus $\dot{m}_{V_{j+1}}$. Equations from (45) to (50) are obtained developing Equations from (27) to (32) as described in Appendix C. The coefficients a_{MLPi} , a_{MLXi} , a_{MLhi} , a_{MLai} , a_{ELPi} , a_{ELhi} , a_{ELai} , a_{MVPi} , a_{MVXi} , a_{MVhi} , a_{MVai} , a_{EVPi} , a_{EVhi} , and a_{EVai} are calculated from Equation (51) to Equation (64).

$$a_{MLPi} \frac{dP}{dt} + a_{MLXi} \frac{dX_{Li}}{dt} + a_{MLhi} \frac{dh_{Li}}{dt} + a_{MLai} \frac{da_i}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} + \dot{m}_{A_i} + \dot{m}_{B_i} + \dot{m}_{cond_i} - \dot{m}_{evap_i} + (1 - k_j) \dot{m}_{V_j} \quad (45)$$

$$\rho_{Li} V_i (1 - a_i) \frac{dX_{Li}}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} (X_{L_{j+1}} - X_{L_i}) - \dot{m}_{L_j} (X_{L_j} - X_{L_i}) + \dot{m}_{A_i} (1 - X_{L_i}) - \dot{m}_{B_i} X_{L_i} - \dot{m}_{cond_i} (X_{L_i} - X_{cond,i}) \quad (46)$$

$$a_{ELPi} \frac{dP}{dt} + a_{ELhi} \frac{dh_{Li}}{dt} + a_{ELai} \frac{da_i}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} (h_{L_{j+1}} - h_{L_i}) - \dot{m}_{L_j} (h_{L_j} - h_{L_i}) + \dot{m}_{A_i} (\tilde{h}_{AL_i} - h_{L_i}) + \dot{m}_{B_i} (\tilde{h}_{BL_i} - h_{L_i}) \quad (47)$$

$$a_{MVPi} \frac{dP}{dt} + a_{MVXi} \frac{dX_{Vi}}{dt} + a_{MVhi} \frac{dh_{Vi}}{dt} + a_{MVai} \frac{da_i}{dt} = k_j \dot{m}_{Vj} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{Vj+1} - \dot{m}_{A_i} - \dot{m}_{B_i} + \dot{m}_{evap_i} - \dot{m}_{cond_i} \quad (48)$$

$$\rho_{Vi} V_i a_i \frac{dX_{Vi}}{dt} = k_j \dot{m}_{Vj} (X_{Vj} - X_{Vi}) - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{Vj+1} (X_{Vj+1} - X_{Vi}) - \dot{m}_{A_i} (1 - X_{Vi}) + \dot{m}_{B_i} X_{Vi} + \dot{m}_{evap_i} (X_{evc} \quad (49)$$

$$a_{EVPi} \frac{dP}{dt} + a_{EVhi} \frac{dh_{Vi}}{dt} + a_{EVai} \frac{da_i}{dt} = k_j \dot{m}_{Vj} (h_{Vj} - h_{Vi}) - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{Vj+1} (h_{Vj+1} - h_{Vi}) - \dot{m}_{A_i} (\tilde{h}_{AV_i} - h_{Vi}) - \dot{m}_{B_i} (\tilde{h} \quad (50)$$

$$a_{MLPi} = V_i (1 - a_i) \frac{\partial \rho_{L_i}}{\partial P} \quad (51)$$

$$a_{MLXi} = V_i (1 - a_i) \frac{\partial \rho_{L_i}}{\partial X} \quad (52)$$

$$a_{MLhi} = V_i (1 - a_i) \frac{\partial \rho_{L_i}}{\partial h} \quad (53)$$

$$a_{MLai} = -V_i \rho_{L_i} \quad (54)$$

$$a_{ELPi} = V_i (a_i - 1) \quad (55)$$

$$a_{ELhi} = V_i \rho_{L_i} (1 - a_i) \quad (56)$$

$$a_{ELai} = V_i P \quad (57)$$

$$a_{MVPi} = V_i a_i \frac{\partial \rho_{V_i}}{\partial P} \quad (58)$$

$$a_{MVXi} = V_i a_i \frac{\partial \rho_{V_i}}{\partial X} \quad (59)$$

$$a_{MVhi} = V_i a_i \frac{\partial \rho_{V_i}}{\partial h} \quad (60)$$

$$a_{MVai} = V_i \rho_{V_i} \quad (61)$$

$$a_{EVPi} = -V_i a_i \quad (62)$$

$$a_{EVhi} = V_i \rho_{V_i} a_i \quad (63)$$

$$a_{EVai} = -V_i P \quad (64)$$

4. Verify that all the calculated \dot{m}_{V_j} have the same direction of the guess. If the directions are not coherent return to point 2 using the calculated direction as new guess.
5. The error is calculated imposing the overall mass balance (see Equation (65)) that is obtained with the sum of the mass balances of every control volume.

$$err = \sum_{i=1}^N (a_{MLPi} + a_{MVPi}) \frac{dP}{dt} + \sum_{i=1}^N a_{MLXi} \frac{dX_{Li}}{dt} + \sum_{i=1}^N a_{MLhi} \frac{dh_{Li}}{dt} + \sum_{i=1}^N a_{MVXi} \frac{dX_{Vi}}{dt} + \sum_{i=1}^N a_{MVhi} \frac{dh_{Vi}}{dt}. \quad (65)$$

6. Verify that the error calculated at point 5 is lower than the maximum accepted error, otherwise return to point 1. The new guess of the pressure variation could be calculated with different methods such as the under-relaxation method, the secant method, the Newton-Raphson method, or a combination of them.

It must be mentioned that Equation (65) is valid when all the control volumes of the component consider the separated flow and thermodynamic equilibrium at the interface (Section 3). In case one or more control volumes add the condition of thermodynamic equilibrium, Equation (66), obtained from the combination of Equations (26) and (65) is used instead of Equation (65). The coefficients a_{MPi} , a_{MXi} , and a_{Mhi} are calculated with Equations (10), (11), and (12) when the thermodynamic equilibrium assumption is applied for a specific control volume, otherwise they are set equal to zero. In contrast, the coefficients a_{MLPi} , a_{MLXi} , a_{MLhi} , a_{MLai} , a_{ELPi} , a_{ELhi} , a_{ELai} , a_{MVPi} , a_{MVPi} , a_{MVXi} , a_{MVhi} , a_{MVai} , a_{EVPi} , a_{EVhi} , and a_{EVai} are set to zero when the thermodynamic equilibrium assumption is considered, otherwise they are calculated from Equation (51) to Equation (64).

$$err = \sum_{i=1}^N (a_{MLPi} + a_{MVPi}) \frac{dP}{dt} + \sum_{i=1}^N a_{MLXi} \frac{dX_{Li}}{dt} + \sum_{i=1}^N a_{MLhi} \frac{dh_{Li}}{dt} + \sum_{i=1}^N a_{MVXi} \frac{dX_{Vi}}{dt} + \sum_{i=1}^N a_{MVhi} \frac{dh_{Vi}}{dt}. \quad (66)$$

3.3 Variable timestep

The explicit integration scheme coupled with a variable time step needs an accurate calculation of the time step. Since the mass, species and energy balances are applied to each sub-volume, the variable time step is calculated in a similar way to that described in Section 1.2, but the conditions on physical quantity variations and masses are applied to the liquid and vapour sub-volumes.

- $\left| \frac{dP}{dt} \right| \Delta t < \Delta P_{max}$
- $\left| \frac{da_i}{dt} \right| \Delta t < \Delta a_{max}$

- $\left| \frac{d X_{Vi}}{dt} \right| \Delta t < \Delta X_{max}$
- $\left| \frac{d X_{Li}}{dt} \right| \Delta t < \Delta X_{max}$
- $\left| \frac{d h_{Li}}{dt} \right| \Delta t < \Delta h_{max}$
- $\left| \frac{d h_{Vi}}{dt} \right| \Delta t < \Delta h_{max}$
- $\frac{M_{Li}}{|\dot{m}_{Lj}|} * 0.5 > \Delta t \quad \text{if } (\dot{m}_{Lj} \neq 0)$
- $\frac{M_{Li-1}}{|\dot{m}_{Lj}|} * 0.5 > \Delta t \quad \text{if } (\dot{m}_{Lj} \neq 0)$
- $\frac{M_{Vi}}{|\dot{m}_{Vj}|} * 0.5 > \Delta t \quad \text{if } (\dot{m}_{Vj} \neq 0)$
- $\frac{M_{Vi-1}}{|\dot{m}_{Vj}|} * 0.5 > \Delta t \quad \text{if } (\dot{m}_{Vj} \neq 0)$
- $\Delta t \leq \Delta t_{max}$

The minimum time step is selected to perform the integration as described in Section 1.2. The threshold Δa_{max} is set equal to 0.05.

4. Dynamic model for incompressible fluid and walls

The dynamic model for incompressible fluid is usually considered for coupling fluids. The temperature variation is calculated through the energy balance in Equation (67).

$$\frac{dT_i}{dt} = \frac{\dot{m}_j h_j - \dot{m}_{j+1} h_{j+1} + \sum \dot{Q}_i}{\rho_i V_i c_{p_i}} \quad (67)$$

Two dynamic models for walls are described. Equation (68) is the energy balance imposed to the single capacitance model that assumes homogenous temperature of the wall, while Equation (69) and Equation (70) are imposed to the nodes of the two capacities model that allocate half of the mass for each node and connects the nodes with a thermal resistance.

$$\frac{dT_{wi}}{dt} = \frac{\sum \dot{Q}_i}{M_{wi} c_{w_i}} \quad (68)$$

$$\frac{dT_{wi,1}}{dt} = \frac{\sum \dot{Q}_{i,1}}{M_{wi}/2 c_{w_i}} \quad (69)$$

$$\frac{dT_{wi,2}}{dt} = \frac{\sum \dot{Q}_{i,2}}{M_{wi}/2 c_{w_i}} \quad (70)$$

Appendix A

The mass conservation equation is Equation (A1)

$$\frac{d(\rho_i V_i)}{dt} = \dot{m}_j - \dot{m}_{j+1} \quad A1$$

The density derivative is Equation (A2), while V_i is constant. Combining Equation (A1) and Equation (A2), Equation (7) is obtained, where a_{MPi} , a_{MXi} , and a_{Mhi} are calculated in Equation (10), Equation (11), and Equation (12).

$$\frac{d\rho_i}{dt} = \frac{\partial\rho_i}{\partial P} \frac{dP}{dt} + \frac{\partial\rho_i}{\partial X} \frac{dX_i}{dt} + \frac{\partial\rho_i}{\partial h} \frac{dh_i}{dt} \quad A2$$

The species conservation equation is Equation (A3).

$$\frac{d(\rho_i V_i X_i)}{dt} = \dot{m}_j X_j - \dot{m}_{j+1} X_{j+1} \quad A3$$

Density and mass fraction are time dependent, thus Equation (A3) becomes Equation (A4)

$$\rho_i V_i \frac{dX_i}{dt} + X_i \frac{d\rho_i V_i}{dt} = \dot{m}_j X_j - \dot{m}_{j+1} X_{j+1} \quad A4$$

Substituting $\frac{d\rho_i V_i}{dt}$ with Equation (A1), Equation (A5) is obtained.

$$\rho_i V_i \frac{dX_i}{dt} = \dot{m}_j (X_j - X_i) - \dot{m}_{j+1} (X_{j+1} - X_i) \quad A5$$

The energy conservation equation is Equation (A6).

$$\frac{d(\rho_i V_i (h_i - v_i P))}{dt} = \dot{m}_j h_j - \dot{m}_{j+1} h_{j+1} + \sum \dot{Q}_i \quad A6$$

Pressure, enthalpy and density are time dependent, while V_i is constant. The energy balance becomes Equation (A7).

$$V_i h_i \frac{d\rho_i}{dt} + V_i \rho_i \frac{dh_i}{dt} - V_i \frac{dP}{dt} = \dot{m}_j h_j - \dot{m}_{j+1} h_{j+1} + \sum \dot{Q}_i \quad A7$$

Substituting the density derivatives with Equation (A2), Equation (A8) is obtained.

$$\left(V_i h_i \frac{\partial\rho_i}{\partial P} - V_i \right) \frac{dP}{dt} + \left(V_i h_i \frac{\partial\rho_i}{\partial h} + V_i \rho_i \right) \frac{dh_i}{dt} - \left(V_i h_i \frac{\partial\rho_i}{\partial X} \right) \frac{dX_i}{dt} = \dot{m}_j h_j - \dot{m}_{j+1} h_{j+1} + \sum \dot{Q}_i \quad A8$$

Appendix B

The mass conservation equation is Equation (B1).

$$\frac{d(\rho_i V_i)}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} + k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} + (1-k_j) \dot{m}_{V_j} - (1-k_{j+1}) \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} \quad B1$$

The density derivative is Equation (A2), while V_i is constant. Combining Equation (B1) and Equation (A2), Equation (B2) is obtained, where a_{MPi} , a_{MXi} , and a_{Mhi} are calculated in Equation (10), Equation (11), and Equation (12).

$$a_{MPi} \frac{dP}{dt} + a_{MXi} \frac{dX_i}{dt} + a_{Mhi} \frac{dh_i}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} + k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} + (1-k_j) \dot{m}_{V_j} - (1-k_{j+1}) \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} \quad B2$$

The species conservation equation is Equation (B3).

$$\frac{d(\rho_i V_i X_i)}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} X_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} X_{L_j} + k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} X_{V_j} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} X_{V_{j+1}} + (1-k_j) \dot{m}_{V_j} X_{L_j}^* - (1-k_{j+1}) \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} X_{L_{j+1}}^* \quad B3$$

Density and mass fraction are time dependent, thus Equation (B3) becomes Equation (B4)

$$\rho_i V_i \frac{dX_i}{dt} + X_i \frac{d(\rho_i V_i)}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} X_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} X_{L_j} + k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} X_{V_j} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} X_{V_{j+1}} + (1-k_j) \dot{m}_{V_j} X_{L_j}^* - (1-k_{j+1}) \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} X_{L_{j+1}}^* \quad B4$$

Substituting $\frac{d(\rho_i V_i)}{dt}$ with Equation (A2), Equation (B5) is obtained.

$$\rho_i V_i \frac{dX_i}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} (X_{L_{j+1}} - X_i) - \dot{m}_{L_j} (X_{L_j} - X_i) + k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} (X_{V_j} - X_i) - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} (X_{V_{j+1}} - X_i) + (1-k_j) \dot{m}_{V_j} (X_{L_j}^* - X_i) - (1-k_{j+1}) \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} (X_{L_{j+1}}^* - X_i) \quad B5$$

The energy conservation equation is Equation (B6)

$$\frac{d(\rho_i V_i (h_i - v_i P))}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} h_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} h_{L_j} + k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} h_{V_j} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} h_{V_{j+1}} + (1-k_j) \dot{m}_{V_j} h_{L_j}^* - (1-k_{j+1}) \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} h_{L_{j+1}}^* \quad B6$$

Pressure, enthalpy and density are time dependent, while V_i is constant. The energy balance becomes Equation (B7).

$$V_i h_i \frac{d\rho_i}{dt} + V_i \rho_i \frac{dh_i}{dt} - V_i \frac{dP}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} h_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} h_{L_j} + k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} h_{V_j} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} h_{V_{j+1}} + (1-k_j) \dot{m}_{V_j} h_{L_j}^* - (1-k_{j+1}) \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} h_{L_{j+1}}^* \quad B7$$

Substituting the density derivatives with Equation (A2), Equation (B8) is obtained.

$$\left(V_i h_i \frac{\partial \rho_i}{\partial P} - V_i \right) \frac{dP}{dt} + \left(V_i h_i \frac{\partial \rho_i}{\partial h} + V_i \rho_i \right) \frac{dh_i}{dt} - V_i \frac{dP}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} h_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} h_{L_j} + k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} h_{V_j} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} h_{V_{j+1}} \quad B8$$

Appendix C

The liquid mass balance is Equation (C1).

$$\frac{d(\rho_{L_i} V_i (1 - a_i))}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} + \dot{m}_{A_j} + \dot{m}_{B_j} + \dot{m}_{cond_i} - \dot{m}_{evap_i} + (1 - k_j) \dot{m}_{V_j} - (1 - k_{j+1}) \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} \quad C1$$

Liquid density and void fraction are time dependent, while V_i is constant. Developing Equation (C1), Equation (C2) is obtained.

$$V_i (1 - a_i) \frac{d\rho_{L_i}}{dt} - \rho_{L_i} V_i \frac{da_i}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} + \dot{m}_{A_j} + \dot{m}_{B_j} + \dot{m}_{cond_i} - \dot{m}_{evap_i} + (1 - k_j) \dot{m}_{V_j} - (1 - k_{j+1}) \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} \quad C2$$

The liquid density derivative is Equation (C3). Combining Equation (C2) and Equation (C3), Equation (45) is obtained.

$$\frac{d\rho_{L_i}}{dt} = \frac{\partial\rho_{L_i}}{\partial P} \frac{dP}{dt} + \frac{\partial\rho_{L_i}}{\partial X} \frac{dX_{L_i}}{dt} + \frac{\partial\rho_{L_i}}{\partial h} \frac{dh_{L_i}}{dt} \quad C3$$

For vapor, Equation (48) is obtained combining Equation (C5) and Equation (C6). Equation (C5) is obtained developing Equation (C4).

$$\frac{d(\rho_{V_i} V_i a_i)}{dt} = k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{A_v} - \dot{m}_{B_v} - \dot{m}_{cond_i} + \dot{m}_{evap_i} \quad C4$$

$$V_i a_i \frac{d\rho_{V_i}}{dt} + \rho_{V_i} V_i \frac{da_i}{dt} = k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{A_v} - \dot{m}_{B_v} - \dot{m}_{cond_i} + \dot{m}_{evap_i} \quad C5$$

$$\frac{d\rho_{V_i}}{dt} = \frac{\partial\rho_{V_i}}{\partial P} \frac{dP}{dt} + \frac{\partial\rho_{V_i}}{\partial X} \frac{dX_{V_i}}{dt} + \frac{\partial\rho_{V_i}}{\partial h} \frac{dh_{V_i}}{dt} \quad C6$$

The liquid species conservation equation is Equation (C7).

$$\frac{d(\rho_{L_i} V_i (1 - a_i) X_{L_i})}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} X_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} X_{L_j} + \dot{m}_{A_j} + \dot{m}_{cond_i} X_{cond_i} - \dot{m}_{evap_i} X_{eva p_i} + (1 - k_j) \dot{m}_{V_j} X_{L_{i-1}} - (1 - k_{j+1}) \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} X_{L_{i-1}} \quad C7$$

Liquid density and mass fraction are time dependent, thus Equation (C7) becomes Equation (C8).

$$X_{L_i} \frac{dM_{L_i}}{dt} + M_{L_i} \frac{dX_{L_i}}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} X_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} X_{L_j} + \dot{m}_{A_j} + \dot{m}_{cond_i} X_{cond_i} - \dot{m}_{evap_i} X_{eva p_i} + (1 - k_j) \dot{m}_{V_j} X_{L_{i-1}} - (1 - k_{j+1}) \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} X_{L_{i-1}} \quad C8$$

Substituting $\frac{dM_{L_i}}{dt}$ with Equation (C1), Equation (46) is obtained.

For vapor, Equation (49) is obtained combining Equation (C10) and Equation (C6). Equation (C10) is obtained developing Equation (C9).

$$\frac{d(\rho_{V_i} V_i a_i X_{V_i})}{dt} = k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} X_{V_j} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} X_{V_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{A_{Vi}} - \dot{m}_{cond_i} X_{cond_i} + \dot{m}_{evap_i} X_{eva p_i} \quad C9$$

$$X_{V_i} \frac{dM_{V_i}}{dt} + M_{V_i} \frac{dX_{V_i}}{dt} = k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} X_{V_j} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} X_{V_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{A_{Vi}} - \dot{m}_{cond_i} X_{cond_i} + \dot{m}_{evap_i} X_{eva p_i} \quad C10$$

The liquid energy conservation equation is Equation (C11).

$$\frac{d(M_{L_i}(h_{L_i} - v_{L_i} P))}{dt} = \dot{m}_{L_{j+1}} h_{L_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{L_j} h_{L_j} + \dot{m}_{A_{Vi}} \tilde{h}_{A_{Vi}} + \dot{m}_{B_{Vi}} \tilde{h}_{B_{Vi}} + \dot{m}_{cond_i} h_{cond_i} - \dot{m}_{evap_i} h_{eva p_i} + (1 - k_j) \dot{m}_{V_j} h_{L_i} \quad C11$$

Liquid mass and enthalpy are time dependent. Combining Equation (C11) and Equation (C3), Equation (47) is obtained.

For vapor, Equation (50) is obtained combining Equation (C12), and Equation (C6).

$$\frac{d(M_{V_i}(h_{V_i} - v_{V_i} P))}{dt} = k_j \dot{m}_{V_j} h_{V_j} - k_{j+1} \dot{m}_{V_{j+1}} h_{V_{j+1}} - \dot{m}_{A_{Vi}} \tilde{h}_{A_{Vi}} - \dot{m}_{B_{Vi}} \tilde{h}_{B_{Vi}} - \dot{m}_{cond_i} h_{cond_i} + \dot{m}_{evap_i} h_{eva p_i} + \sum \dot{Q}_V \quad C12$$

Nomenclature

A : Total heat transfer area (m^2)
 a : void fraction ($m_{vapor}^3 m_{vapor+liquid}^{-3}$)
 A_c : Cross sectional Area (m^2)
 \tilde{C} : partial specific heat ($J kg^{-1} K^{-1}$)
 \bar{C} : partial molar specific heat ($J mol^{-1} K^{-1}$)
 c_p : specific heat ($J kg^{-1} K^{-1}$)
 D : diameter (m)
err: error
 E : void fraction of the packed bed ($m^3 m^{-3}$)
 F : mass transfer coefficient ($mol m^{-2} s^{-1}$)
 f : liquid mass flow rate correction factor (-)
 g : gravitational acceleration ($m s^{-2}$)
 H : height (m)
 h : specific enthalpy ($J kg^{-1}$)
 \tilde{h} : specific partial enthalpy ($J kg^{-1}$)
 \bar{h} : specific partial molar enthalpy ($J mol^{-1}$)
 H_d : dynamic liquid hold up ($m^3 m^{-3}$)
 H_s : static liquid hold up ($m^3 m^{-3}$)
 k : vapor fraction of the mass flow rate (-)
 L_c : characteristic length (m)
 M : mass (kg)
 \dot{m} : mass flow rate ($kg s^{-1}$)
 \ddot{m} : mass flux ($kg s^{-1} m^{-2}$)
 N : Number (-)
 \dot{n} : molar flux ($mol m^{-2} s^{-1}$)
 P : pressure (Pa)
 \dot{Q} : heat flow rate (W)
 q : vapor quality (-)
 t : time (s)
 T : temperature (K)
 u : specific internal energy ($J kg^{-1}$)
 V : volume (m^3)
 \dot{V} : volumetric flow rate ($m^3 s^{-1}$)
 v : specific volume ($m^3 kg^{-1}$)

Greeks:
 α : heat transfer coefficient ($W m^{-2} K^{-1}$)
 Δ : difference (-)
 μ : dynamic viscosity ($kg m^{-1} s^{-1}$)
 ρ : density ($kg m^{-3}$)

ϕ : rate factor (-)
 ψ : correction factor (-)

Subscripts:

∞ : bulk

0 : interface conditions

cond: condensed

conv: convective

evap: evaporated

ext: external

h: heat

i: node center of control volume

\int *i*: interface

ij: boundary of the control volume

L : liquid

m: mass

tot : total

V : vapor

W : wall

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